

Conductometric Study of the Reaction Between Zirconyl Chloride and Sodium Tungstate

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Joshi and Bhargava¹ studied spectrophotometrically the complex formation of ammoniacal copper sulphate with picric acid. The complex obtained was in the form of an olive green precipitate and for its study Job's continuous variation method was applied to the supernatant liquid. Good results were obtained for equimolar and non-equimolar solutions. In the present investigation the author observed that when aqueous solutions of zirconyl chloride and sodium tungstate were mixed in different ratios, in each mixture a white precipitate immediately settled down. The conductometric measurements of supernatant liquids showed interesting results. The author was, therefore, inspired to take up the present reaction.

The reaction was studied using A.R. (B.D.H.) samples of zirconyl chloride and sodium tungstate. The conductivity measurements were done by "Doran" conductivity bridge and dip-type conductivity cell with WTW 1000 cycle oscillator. All measurements were carried out at a temperature of 28°.

The reaction was first studied by monovariation-method². The solutions used were of the concentration of M/80. In one set of reaction the volume of zirconyl chloride was kept constant (5 ml) while in the second set the volume of Na-tungstate. For both the sets clear breaks are obtained in the graph where the composition of the mixture is 1 : 1 (fig. 1)

Fig. 1

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1. Joshi and Bhargava, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 19.
2. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 284.

The reaction was then studied by applying the Job's continuous variation method⁹ for equimolar (M/60 and M/80) solutions and measuring the conductivity of supernatant liquid. It is observed that a peak is obtained in the curve, where the composition of the mixture is 50 percent each of zirconyl-chloride and Na-tungstate (fig. 2.) Here the conductance difference, unlike the complex formed remaining in solution, of the mixture minus the sum of conductance due to the two constituents is negative. The peak is obtained when the numerical value of the negative conductance difference is plotted against the percentage volume of one of the components, viz., the volume of the Na-tungstate solution.

Fig. 2

It has been observed in monovariation as well as in continuous variation method that complete precipitation occurs when the two solutions in the mixture are 50 percent each. The supernatant liquid at this stage is perfectly clear. For any other ratio of the two solutions the supernatant liquid is turbid showing incomplete precipitation. The clear supernatant liquid is tested for chloride ions. It has been observed that it gives curdy white precipitate with silver-nitrate solution showing the presence of chloride ions. The author therefore proposes that the precipitate, obtained by mixing zirconyl chloride and Na-tungstate solutions, is the complex compound $ZrOWO_4$ formed by the reaction :

It has been mentioned in the preceding paragraph that when aqueous solutions of zirconyl chloride and sodium-tungstate are mixed in stoichiometric ratio, the supernatant liquid is perfectly clear. From this fact the author proposes that the reaction can be conveniently used as one of the methods for the quantitative estimation of zirconium and further work in this regard is in progress.

The author expresses his gratitude to Prof. A. K. Bhattacharya, Head of the Chemistry Dept., University of Sagar, for providing laboratory facilities. Thanks are also due to the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, Govt. of India, for financial assistance.

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Received May 11, 1964.